

OBJECTIVES INTENDED IN THE CONCEPT OF EDUCATIONAL WORK OUTSIDE THE CLASSROOM AND SCHOOL

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Abstract. *This article discusses the educational impact on students as a result of extracurricular activities and the goals envisaged in the concept of these educational activities.*

Keywords: *extracurricular activities, circle, the concept of educational activities, extracurricular activities, professional education, scientific outlook.*

The out-of-class form of training allows students to develop a scientific worldview, work culture and love for nature, as well as to develop independent observation skills, interest in learning, and initiative. In all types of extracurricular activities, uniform educational processes implemented in a specific system and development are observed. All types of extracurricular activities are interrelated and complement each other. Interest in working with living plants and animals is usually born in the classroom, and students who are especially interested are all of the teacher's. In addition to their mandatory tasks, they also carry out more complex tasks that they undertake voluntarily.

The teacher joins the students who are very interested in the course into the circle of young naturalists. The teacher tries to show the results of the work of a group of young naturalists or a group of students working on creating a textbook not only in the classroom, but also at public events: parties, conferences, exhibitions, etc. Thus, direct and indirect connections with the lesson are made in extracurricular activities.

Students' interests are often very narrow, limited to being in an amateurish relationship with some animals. The task of the teacher is to expand the interest of students, to educate educated people who love science and can study nature.

Types of work outside the classroom allow students to move from individual work to collective work, after which it acquires a social direction, which is of great importance for education.

Group training. Circles of young naturalists. Among the extracurricular activities in biology, the circle of young naturalists takes the leading place as the main nucleus in the organization of other activities.

In school practice, various activities performed by a group of biology students after class are often considered to be science activities, even though they are mostly extracurricular activities.

The purpose of the Young Naturalist Club is to interest students in biology, to deepen and expand their knowledge, to form observational and experimental skills in them, and to help foster understanding of nature. In the circle of natural scientists, work is carried out systematically, based on a certain plan, with a voluntary, but permanent composition of students.

The classification of natural science circles according to the biology course taught at school allows, on the one hand, to get to know one of them a little deeper, and on the other hand, to use the results of some experiments in lessons.

Students' work in the circle should be considered as a means of education. Most of the time, when accepting students to the club, teachers look at their good mastery of biology and good discipline. But the experience of the best teachers shows that as a result of group classes, unachieving students become interested in biology, and poorly behaved students behave much better.

In the circle, it is important to combine individual, independent, creative and responsible work of each student with collective, social work.

Taking into account the psychology of V, VI, VII graders, it is not appropriate to set a specific time goal for them or to keep them busy with the same work. The number of students in the circle usually does not exceed 15-20. If there are many applicants, two groups will be organized at different times. According to the experience of many schools, it is better to conduct club training once a week or twice a month.

The work of the circle is diverse; it is necessary to use both individual and collective work methods and build on a common topic that includes familiarization with various experimental works and literature.

Out-of-class biological excursions can be conducted on various topics in all biology subjects. In the summer, multi-day biological excursions are especially interesting, which students call expeditions.

Multi-day expeditions can be complex and special. Complex expeditions are conducted in various departments of biology (botany, zoology), geology and geography, and more often in connection with the "research" of a number of issues of local history, issues of the history of the country and folklore. Several experts-teachers (mostly biologists and geographers) participate in leading the expedition. In such conditions, it will be convenient to divide students into squads. The expedition is carried out on foot or, if possible, by boat along the river.

Local history and nature in all biological excursions. the purpose of protection is implied.

The purpose of the scientific evenings is to draw attention to scientific issues, interest them, and direct them to independent reading of scientific and artistic books. Table at scientific night, picture experiments, live animals and plants, book exhibitions are organized, posters are hung showing what can be seen in which museum, etc. The most important thing is the cognitive biological content of the night.

Decorating the night is also important. The stage will be decorated with plants, cards, portraits, pictures related to the theme of the night will be hung on the wall. Tablets are quickly changed during the reports.

Individual extracurricular activities. There are always amateur students who voluntarily take assignments from the teacher to work at home or in the living corner of the school. Some students create their living nature corner at home. To such students, the teacher gives instructions for conducting experiments at home or in the living corner, or on the school site, and for conducting observations in the summer, in addition to the mandatory assignments related to the program given in the classroom. Individual extracurricular activities are essentially optional homework and extracurricular activities.

Studying outside the classroom develops students' thinking, increases interest in the subject. Along with all the activities at school, it cultivates the desire to be in constant communication with the book. This is one of the most important factors in educating our youth.

When conducting extracurricular activities, the teacher should be in close contact with the school library: he should take into account the availability of necessary books and the students' demand for them; together with the librarian, it is necessary to organize an exhibition of recommended literature and book discussion nights on a specific topic.

The purpose of this is to provide students with more knowledge and practical skills from various departments of labor and education than the school program. These classes are of great importance in guiding students to choose a profession, because students who want to continue studying or working in special (biology, agriculture, medicine) educational institutions are enrolled in optional courses. The educational activities carried out in accordance with the students' vocational education program are considered the minimum required for each student who receives information. However, this type of students' cocktail activity cannot satisfy the individual requirements of some students and their interest in other areas of their academic and technical knowledge. We can fill this deficiency by conducting activities outside the classroom and school among students. Out-of-class and extra-curricular activities on technique and cocktail are organized in the form of circles. The types of these circles are determined by the issues they have to solve and their content. As circles that differ depending on the type of craft: carpentry, metalwork, turning, automobile, electrical engineering, service, tailoring, cooking), agricultural craft, etc. can be indicated. The goal of such clubs, which are organized according to the cocktail club, is to expand and deepen the students' special technical knowledge and cocktail skills, as well as the skills of this type of cocktail. The members of the circle take an active part in equipping educational workshops and offices, providing them with visual aids and equipment, technical and technological documents, etc.

REFERENCES

1. Roila Yuldoshvoyevna Xaydarova. ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN THE FIELD OF TECHNOLOGY IN PREPARING PUPILS FOR EDUCATION ON THE BASIS OF FOLK CRAFTS. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 4 APRIL 2023. 100-101p.
2. Jalilova D.U. Psychological And Technological Features of Increasing the Efficiency of Educational Activity of Talented Students in Presidential Schools. Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices ISSN NO: 2770-2367 (<https://zienjournals.com>).
3. Roila Yuldoshvoyevna Xaydarova. METHODOLOGY OF FORMATION OF COMPETENCES OF PUPILS' INTEREST IN NATIONAL CRAFTS BASED ON THE CLUSTER APPROACH. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 4 MARCH 2023. 373-374p.
4. https://t.me/jalilova_dilshoda_2292
5. https://t.me/ilmiy_yordam_beraman
6. <https://cyberleninka.ru>
7. <http://scientists.uz>